

Feasibility study of single-well dual-cable DAS for micro-seismic monitoring of geothermal operations

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Abstract

Distributed acoustic sensing (DAS) that uses optical fibres as sensing units, is attracting increasing interest for micro-seismic monitoring in geothermal projects. Standard optical fibres provide one-component measurements along the fibre and this poses challenges in determining certain characteristics of the source, such as its azimuth and its full moment tensor. Full source characteristics can be obtained via offset downhole measurements and/or measurements from horizontal well sections but these come with substantial extra costs. This paper proposes a single-well dual-cable DAS configuration to reduce the need for drilling additional wells or sections, where two DAS cables are assumed to be positioned within a single vertical well at opposite sides of the well. Synthetic DAS signals are generated by an open-source code that assumes plane layered media, and are used to study the feasibility of the dual-cable DAS for localising a seismic source and resolving its moment tensor. A localisation procedure is presented, and a sensitivity analysis of localization accuracy is conducted with respect to source parameters and noise levels. In addition, an analysis is performed to assess the resolvability of the moment-tensor components from the dual-cable DAS configuration. Results suggest the source location can be fully determined, yet low signal-to-noise ratio and azimuth close to 0° (North, aligned with the two cables) lead to a decrease in accuracy. The full moment tensor can be resolved only if the epicentral distance is 5 meters or less, while non-Double-Couple components can be reliably resolved with an epicentral distance up to 20 meters, showing improvement compared to installations with a single cable. Geo-mechanical simulation of thermo-hydraulic stimulation to a synthetic reservoir shows that the propagation of the main tensile fracture in the direction of maximum initial stress σ_H that happens within 20 m can be well monitored and understood, while the understanding of the tensile fracture branching in other directions relies on the resolvability of the moment tensor component M_{xy} . Overall, the results demonstrate that a single-well dual-cable configuration has the potential for monitoring and understanding near-borehole micro-seismic events induced during geothermal reinjection and stimulation operations.

Keywords: Micro-seismic monitoring, Distributed acoustic sensing, moment tensor, geothermal energy

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1 **Highlights**

- 2 • A single-well dual-cable DAS configuration is proposed to facilitate micro-seismic source localisation and
3 mechanisms inversion.
- 4 • Source location can be fully determined.
- 5 • The localisation accuracy is not sensitive to frequency varying from 50 Hz to 200 Hz, but can be reduced
6 by low signal-to-noise ratio.
- 7 • Resolvability analysis shows non-DC components of sources with epicentral distance less than 20 meters
8 can be reliably resolved.
- 9 • Geo-mechanical simulation demonstrates that stimulation induced near-borehole tensile fractures are likely
10 to be able to be localised and understood.

11 1. Introduction

12 Micro-seismic monitoring entails the detection of small-scale rock-failure events with magnitude less than 0 on
13 the Richter scale and frequency ranging roughly from 0.1 Hz - 10 kHz (Meng et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2016)).
14 It has been widely used in geothermal and/or underground storage projects since its inception in the 1970s
15 (Warpinski, 2009). Its most notable application is mapping stimulation operations to provide information on
16 the stimulated volume, fracture geometry and complexity and geo-mechanical responses (Le Calvez et al., 2007;
17 Martyushev et al., 2024). This gives information of the subsurface stimulation processes in 3D continuously,
18 allowing the improvement of operations and to react to unexpected issues, e.g. induced seismicity (Li et al.,
19 2019), in real time. For example, micro-seismic monitoring of six hydraulic fracturing tests at the M-site field,
20 a fluvial sandstone reservoir in the Piceance basin of Colorado, from multilevel and triaxial seismic receivers in
21 two wells were used to image the fracture height, length and azimuth and to correlate the geometry with the
22 injection volume and type (Warpinski et al., 1999). The imaged fractures were also compared with a fracture
23 model, showing good agreement while also indicating a lack of downward growth in the model, suggesting other
24 constraints on the fracture maybe missing, or less likely, incorrect stress data (Warpinski et al., 1999). Shapiro
25 et al. (2006) interpreted micro-seismic data of two hydraulic fracturing experiments in the Carthage Cotton
26 Valley tight gas field, in eastern Texas, using the well-known analytical hydraulic fracturing model, i.e. the
27 so-called PKN model that describes the propagation of a straight planar height-fixed vertical fracture due to
28 injection of fracturing fluid (Valkó and Economides, 1995). Their results suggested the fracture growth during a
29 dominant part of the injection duration could be mainly controlled by the fluid loss effects and they demonstrated
30 the estimation of the permeability of the fracture and of the reservoir based on the triggering front and back
31 front curves of the induced micro-seismic events on the spatial-temporal plots (Shapiro et al., 2006). Cornet
32 and Jianmin (1995) reported that a network of 15 subsurface 3D seismic stations was employed to monitor the
33 injection tests conducted at the granite test site at Le Mayet De Montagne, central France, and the inversion of
34 the micro-seismic data, together with measurements from hydraulic tests on pre-existing fractures with known
35 orientations, led to the determination of the regional stress field and the identification of the fault plane for
36 each of the focal mechanisms. Analysis of the recorded micro-seismic events during hydraulic fracturing tests
37 in the context of enhanced geothermal system (EGS) at the Sanford Underground Research Facility, South
38 Dakota, confirmed a complex mixed-mode fracture network comprised of multi-strand hydraulic fractures and
39 shear-reactivated pre-existing weak planes (Schoenball et al., 2020). In short, microseismic monitoring is an
40 essential tool to ensure efficiency and safety of operations in the subsurface.

41 Recently, distributed acoustic sensing (DAS), an alternative to traditional point sensors like geophones, has
42 been attracting increasing attention for micro-seismic monitoring. DAS relies on elastic Rayleigh scattering
43 resulting from inhomogeneities in an optical fibre as encountered by a pulse of light. The optical fibre itself acts
44 as a densely distributed sensors that senses the strain or strain rate over a defined length, the so-called gauge
45 length (Hartog, 2017; Hasani, 2024). A unique feature of DAS is that it can provide continuous measurements
46 over an entire well with high spatial and temporal resolution (Lellouch et al., 2020; Mad Zahir et al., 2023).
47 Moreover, compared to the conventional sensors such as geophones, DAS can be deployed in extremely harsh
48 environments, e.g. geothermal wells, because the optical fibre is protected by primary polymer coating. DAS
49 can be permanently installed behind well casings, thereby increasing the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) (Lellouch

50 [et al., 2020](#)) and allowing regular operations to continue unimpeded. This eliminates the need to drill offset
51 monitoring boreholes, thus saving costs. Yet, limitations exist and need to be considered when designing a
52 DAS installation. DAS senses the axial strain or strain rate along the fibre, therefore only providing a one-
53 component (1C) signal and leading to broadside insensitivity, i.e. no recording of wave motion perpendicular
54 to the cable orientation. The 1C nature of DAS has limited its capability of fully locating the micro-seismic
55 events, particularly in polarity analysis ([Lellouch et al., 2020](#)) and source-mechanism inversion.

56 Fully localising cracking events is important for tracking the stimulated volume of hydraulic fracturing, un-
57 derstanding in-situ stress states and stress rotation during stimulation. Some approaches have been proposed
58 to fully localise the micro-seismic source. One of the possible solutions is to install optical fibres in multiple
59 wells, e.g. the multi-well installations at the Hydraulic Fracturing Test Site 2 R & D program in the Per-
60 mian Delaware Basin ([Ciezobka, 2021](#)) and the multi-well DAS micro-seismic monitoring program conducted
61 in Northern Nevada ([Dadi et al., 2024](#)). Alternatively, optical fibres can be installed all the way along vertical
62 and horizontal/over-deviated borehole sections, such as in the field case reported in ([Webster et al., 2013](#)) and
63 ([Verdon et al., 2020](#)), and the field test implemented during hydraulic stimulation in the Meramec formation
64 ([Karrenbach et al., 2019](#)). However, drilling offset wells or horizontal wells is often costly and is not always
65 possible due to restricted surface and geological conditions. Other methods have been proposed to localise
66 the source but with requirements on the geological conditions. For instance, [Lellouch et al.](#) ([Lellouch et al.,](#)
67 [2022](#)) proposed to locate micro-seismic events based on recorded signals from a single horizontal DAS cable, but
68 their method requires conditions where the reservoir can act as a waveguide. [Baird et al.](#) ([Baird et al., 2020](#))
69 takes advantage of the anisotropy (vertical transverse isotropic) of the media, where the vertical and horizontal
70 shear-wave velocities differ, to fully constrain the location via a single horizontal DAS cable. Although both
71 methods show promising results, they need a-priori information and therefore limit their approach to a more
72 general situation.

73 Determining the source mechanism of near-field micro-seismicity is essential to understand the physics of the
74 stimulation processes, thus identifying the contributions from hydraulic fractures and natural fractures (or weak
75 planes) ([Nolen-Hoeksema and Ruff, 2001](#); [Schoenball et al., 2020](#)). The seismic moment tensor can provide an
76 estimate of the source mechanism and can be determined from the inversion of the observed seismic waveforms
77 ([Wu et al., 2023](#)). The moment tensor is a symmetric and second-order tensor which has six independent
78 components. It is generally decomposed into three elementary parts: including isotropic (ISO), double-couple
79 (DC) and compensated linear vector dipole (CLVD) parts, corresponding to volumetric changes (explosion
80 or implosion), pure shear failure and tensile failure without volumetric change respectively ([Vavryčuk, 2015](#)).
81 Therefore, the moment tensor is a direct representation of the stresses (or strain) in the vicinity of the source,
82 and allows the estimation of orthogonal strain axes for each event and identification of the stress state at the
83 front of stimulated area and the potential failure planes ([Baig and Urbancic, 2010](#)). For example, moment
84 tensor inversion was performed by [Ohtsu \(1991\)](#) based on P-wave amplitude from eight micro-seismic events
85 recorded during small-scale hydro-fracturing test in siliceous sandstone at the Imaichi underground power plant.
86 Their results suggested tensile cracks occurred in the outer boundary with crack-opening motions perpendicular
87 to pre-existing joints, while shear cracks occurred mainly near the treatment borehole with motions parallel
88 to the joint plane. Studies on induced micro-seismicity from hydro-fracturing tests at the Hijiori (Japan) hot

89 dry dock geothermal facility (Sasaki, 1998) and at the KTB borehole in North-East Bavaria (Germany) (Jost
90 et al., 1998) suggested best-fit DC focal mechanisms without significant volumetric component, indicating shear
91 failures. Sasaki (1998) has shown that seismic energy radiated from a tensile failure is small as compared
92 with that of a shear failure, resulting in less detectability of tensile cracking events. In contrast, non-DC
93 components, corresponding to tensile failures, have been reported in the results of moment tensor inversion
94 of signals recorded during hydraulic fracturing tests at the M-site field, Colorado (Nolen-Hoeksema and Ruff,
95 2001), at the European Hot Dry Rock (HDR) site of Soultz-sous-Forets, France (Cuenot et al., 2006), at the
96 Coso geothermal field, California (Julian et al., 2007), and in the Carthage Cotton Valley, Texas (Šílený et al.,
97 2009). Yet, the non-DC components cannot be reliably resolved from a single vertical array of receivers, thus
98 leading to simplified assumptions on only deviatoric mechanisms (Nolen-Hoeksema and Ruff, 2001; Šílený et al.,
99 2009).

100 Before the non-trivial moment-tensor inversion, resolvability analysis is valuable to assess whether the unknowns
101 can be accurately retrieved from an inversion (Vera Rodriguez et al., 2011). Resolvability of the full moment
102 tensor based on synthetic data has been investigated for three-component (3C) geophones (particle velocities)
103 (Nolen-Hoeksema and Ruff, 2001; Vavryčuk, 2007; Vera Rodriguez et al., 2011) and for DAS (1C strain/strain
104 rate) (Vera Rodriguez and Wuestefeld, 2020; Bader et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2023) in single and multiple vertical
105 wells. For example, Vera Rodriguez and Wuestefeld (2020) analytically examined the resolvability from two
106 vertical DAS cables, separated at least 50 m from each other and aligned with the coordinate axes x_1 and x_2 ,
107 respectively, with the source at the origin. This configuration ensures enough focal coverage to have a robust
108 resolution of five components. And if one of the cables is moved away from the coordinate axes, the full moment
109 tensor can be resolved (Vera Rodriguez and Wuestefeld, 2020). However, this configuration indicates that an
110 additional well needs to be drilled, which is expensive.

111 To mitigate the need to drill additional boreholes, well sections, or a-priori information to constrain near-borehole
112 micro-seismic events, we propose a dual-cable DAS configuration in a single vertical well. This configuration
113 assumes two DAS cables positioned at opposite sides of a single vertical borehole, as is shown in Fig. 1a. The
114 localisation and resolvability analysis based on signals from this configuration with such a small distance (i.e.
115 borehole diameter) between the two DAS cables has not been studied before. In this paper, synthetic DAS
116 signals are generated by the open-source code Computer Programs in Seismology (CPS) (Herrmann, 2013) that
117 assumes plane-layered media, i.e. 3D media with heterogeneities only in the vertical direction. It is used to
118 show the feasibility of using this dual-cable configuration to improve the constraint of the micro-seismic events
119 compared to the single-cable configuration, including the source localisation and resolvability of moment tensor.
120 The key questions that will be addressed in this paper, with regard to the single-well dual-cables DAS: (1) can
121 we fully localise the source? (2) is the localisation accuracy sensitive to source frequency, noise, source azimuth
122 and mechanism? (3) is the moment tensor fully resolvable? (4) how can it be used to understand stimulation
123 operations?

124 In the following, the numerical model used in the investigation is presented in Section 2. The demonstration
125 of the localisation method to determine the source depth (H), source-to-borehole epicentral distance (D_0) and
126 source to borehole azimuth (θ), defined in Fig. 1a is presented in Section 3, including a sensitivity analysis.
127 In Section 4, the resolvability of the moment tensor via one- and dual-cable DAS array in one single vertical

128 borehole is compared and discussed. In Section 5, the application of this dual-cable DAS to monitor stimulation
 129 operations is discussed based on a geo-mechanical simulation of stimulation operation to a synthetic reservoir,
 130 followed by a conclusions section.

(a) Description of dual-cable DAS configuration

(b) Definition of parameters used for source locating

Fig. 1: Description of the geometry of the dual-cable DAS configuration

131 2. Generating DAS signals

132 To generate synthetic DAS signals, a model using the so-called reflectivity method is used. The reflectivity
 133 method assumes plane-layered media and inhomogeneities occur only in the vertical direction. Analytical
 134 solutions are obtained in the frequency–horizontal-wavenumber domain, and the time-space domain responses
 135 are obtained by a numerical evaluation of the horizontal-wavenumber integral. This all is implemented in the
 136 open-source code Computer Program in Seismology (Jost and Herrmann, 1989; Herrmann, 2013). First, we
 137 define the coordinate system with North being along x with unit vector \mathbf{e}_x , East being along y with unit vector
 138 \mathbf{e}_y , and the downward being z with unit vector \mathbf{e}_z . The model domain is depicted in Fig. 2. A 1000-meter thick
 139 layer is constructed with two half-spaces on top and at the bottom. The layer is isotropic and homogeneous.
 140 A borehole with diameter of 0.5 m is placed vertically through the layer. Two DAS cables are installed at
 141 opposite sides of the borehole, one at the North and the other at the South, from a depth of 445 m to 555 m.
 142 A point-force source is excited at a depth of 500 m, with its distribution in time given by a Ricker wavelet, a
 143 second-derivative of a Gaussian. The source-to-borehole azimuth is 45° (North is 0° while East is 90°). The
 144 DAS has a gauge length (L_G) of 2.5 m, over which the strain is averaged (over three channels) with a channel
 145 spacing (L_C , the distance between two adjacent channels or say points) of 1.25 m. With this configuration,
 146 there is therefore 87 channels on a each DAS cable. Other parameters used in the model are presented in Tab.
 147 1, with the parameters selected to be realistic, but otherwise have no specific significance.

148 The output used from the model is the point strain at the defined DAS channels. However, DAS measures
 149 averaged strain over gauge length, which therefore dominates the spatial resolution (Hasani, 2024). The following
 150 equation is then performed to get the averaged strain:

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{zz}^m = \frac{1}{L_G} \int_{z_m - L_G/2}^{z_m + L_G/2} \epsilon_{zz}^m dz \quad (1)$$

151 where, $\bar{\epsilon}_{zz}^m$ and ϵ_{zz}^m is the averaged and point strain at the m th channel respectively, z_m is the depth of the m th
 152 channel. Since the gauge length is 2.5 m while channel spacing is 1.25 m, there are three channels over which
 153 the strain is averaged for a single channel.

Fig. 2: Description of the numerical model with t dual-cable DAS configuration

Table 1: Input parameters for model to generate synthetic DAS signals

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
P-wave velocity	V_p	3200	m/s
S-wave velocity	V_s	1847	m/s
sampling interval	dt	16	ms
source mechanism	$\mathbf{F} = F_0 \mathbf{e}_z$	2×10^5	N
source function		Ricker wavelet	
source frequency	f_0	200	Hz
source epicentral distance	D_0	40	m
source depth	H	500	m
source azimuth	θ	45	$^\circ$

154 3. Localisation method

155 3.1. Introduction to the localisation method

156 For optical fibres installed along the borehole (either behind casing or somehow coupled to the inner part of the
 157 casing) to monitor micro-seismic activity during stimulation operations, the depth of the micro-seismic events
 158 is likely to be within the range of the DAS cable's length. In this case, the source depth H is the easiest
 159 to determine from DAS signals, namely picking the apex of the P- and S-wave arrivals along the fibres. In
 160 addition, the epicentral distance D_0 can be determined by comparing the actual curvature of the arrivals to the
 161 theoretical curvatures and selecting the one which best matches it, with the assumption that the wave velocity
 162 is known a priori, e.g. from logs.

163 When it comes to determining the source azimuth θ , we take advantage of the time difference Δt^m between
164 arrivals on the m th channels on DAS cable 1 and cable 2, due to them being on opposite sides of the borehole.
165 The time difference multiplied by the known wave velocity can give us the distance difference ($\Delta L^m = D_1^m - D_2^m$,
166 defined in Fig. 1b) from the source to the m th channels on cables 1 and 2, which is a function of the source
167 azimuth. For example, this distance difference for the channel at the same depth with the source is shown in
168 Fig. 3. One possible method to get the time difference is by simply picking the arrival times at the different
169 cables. However, this method is highly dependent on the picking accuracy and restricted by the sampling
170 rate. We therefore use a signal-difference approach which is very sensitive to small time differences. The signal
171 difference is based on the signal attribute known as the Normalised Root-Mean-Square (NRMS) difference that
172 is independent of the sampling rate, which will be clarified below.

Fig. 3: Distance difference between cables 1 and 2, as a function of source azimuth at channel at same depth of the source.

173 The Normalised Root-Mean-Square difference, is defined as:

$$\Delta_{NRMS}(a(t), b(t)) = \frac{2\mathcal{A}_{RMS}(|a(t)| - |b(t)|)}{\mathcal{A}_{RMS}(a(t)) + \mathcal{A}_{RMS}(b(t))} \quad (2)$$

174 where $a(t)$ and $b(t)$ are the two sets of DAS signals. Non-standard absolute values are used in this definition
175 since they are useful when the two signals show opposite signs, for example when the azimuth is 90° and the
176 source is a F_x , generating two opposite-sign signals on the two DAS cables.

177 \mathcal{A}_{RMS} is the Root-Mean-Square amplitude, defined as:

$$\mathcal{A}_{RMS}(x(t)) = \sqrt{\frac{\int_{t_1}^{t_2} x^2(t) dt}{t_2 - t_1}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{N_1}^{N_2} x_i^2}{N_2 - N_1}} \quad (3)$$

178 where N_1 and N_2 are the starting and ending time samples within the specific time window $t_1 - t_2$.

179 With this definition, the Δ_{NRMS} between the m th channel on cable 1 and the m th channel on cable 2 can be
180 obtained, represented by the “observed” Δ_{NRMS}^m . To determine the time difference Δt^m , this observed Δ_{NRMS}^m
181 is compared against a series of pre-computed Δ_{NRMS} to identify the best-fit Δ_{NRMS} . Once identified, the time
182 difference associated with the best-fit Δ_{NRMS} and its neighbouring values are interpolated to get the accurate

183 Δt^m . More details of the pre-computed Δ_{NRMS} can be found in [Appendix A](#)

184 Once the time difference Δt^m is determined, the corresponding difference in distance (ΔL^m) can be obtained,
 185 which is used to back-calculate the azimuth θ^m based on the relation, for example, shown in Fig. 3. The final
 186 azimuth θ is obtained by averaging the θ^m of all the channels along the cable. Note that, as shown in Fig.
 187 3, one ΔL gives two possible azimuths. Yet, this can be resolved by installing a third cable in the well or by
 188 utilising the signal attenuation due to the fluid in the borehole. Since the case of a third cable is not the focus
 189 of this work, it will not be discussed further.

190 3.2. Base example

191 In this section, we demonstrate the localisation method based on a base example. The DAS configuration is
 192 the same as before, i.e., as shown in Fig. 2 with the parameters as given in Tab. 1. Fig. 4a presents the strain
 193 signal on DAS cable 1.

194 The depth of the source can quite easily be picked via the apex of the hyperbola in Fig. 4a, i.e. at 500 m. The
 195 epicentral distance can be obtained via a comparison of the curvature of the observed arrivals on DAS cable 1
 196 to the theoretical curvature (Fig. 4b); in this case the S-wave arrival is taken since it is the strongest arrival.
 197 A best fit of 42 m is obtained, while the true distance is 40 m. The error in the determined epicentral distance
 198 is partly from the time interval used to calculate the theoretical curvatures and partly from the accuracy of the
 199 picking (in this case the S-wave). Yet, the result remains in an acceptable range.

Fig. 4: Strain signals on DAS cable 1 due to a vertical point force (a) and method to determine epicentral distance (b).

200 Next we show how to determine the azimuth. Since the time difference in the signals is symmetric with respect
 201 to the channel at the source depth, only channels on the first half of (above the source depth) the DAS cable
 202 are considered where the channel numbering goes from top to bottom. Fig. 5 shows the observed Δ_{NRMS}^{DAS} and
 203 the determined azimuth at each channel. The result shows that the averaged azimuth is 46.8° , demonstrating
 204 a satisfactory accuracy when compared to the real azimuth (45°).

Fig. 5: Determination of averaged azimuth by comparing the observed Δ_{NRMS}^m with the pre-computed Δ_{NRMS} library. Channel number 1 indicates the top channel at the depth of 445 m, while channel number 44 indicates the channel at the source depth of 500 m. Due to symmetry, the channels from 500 m to 555 m are not shown here.

205 3.3. Sensitivity analysis

206 In this section, the sensitivity to frequency content, noise level, source mechanism and azimuth is investigated
 207 to evaluate their influence on the accuracy of the localisation. Since the advantage of the dual-cable DAS
 208 configuration mainly lies in its improvement in determination of the azimuth, we focus on that only and will
 209 not show the sensitivity of the depth and epicentral distance to the above mentioned parameters.

210 3.3.1. Sensitivity to source frequency

211 The frequency of the micro-seismic events induced during hydraulic stimulation is commonly in the range of tens
 212 to hundreds of Hz (Maxwell and Cipolla, 2011; Van der Baan et al., 2013; Grechka et al., 2021). Therefore, the
 213 influence of the central source frequency of 50 Hz, 100 Hz and 200 Hz on the accuracy is compared. Fig. 6 shows
 214 the DAS signals for source frequencies of 50 Hz and 100 Hz, as well as their determined azimuths. Together
 215 with Fig. 5b, which shows the case for the frequency of 200 Hz, the results suggest that the accuracy to predict
 216 the azimuth is not sensitive to frequency in the range from 50 Hz to 200 Hz. However, for low-frequency events
 217 (< 50 Hz), the large wavelengths may result in negligible differences between signals positioned on opposite
 218 sides of a 0.5 m diameter borehole. The trend of the decreasing Δ_{NRMS}^{DAS} with reduced frequency can be seen in
 219 Fig. 6, of which the right axis shows the corresponding Δ_{NRMS}^{DAS} , demonstrating a higher Δ_{NRMS}^{DAS}
 220 of $f = 100$ Hz than that of $f = 50$ Hz.

221 3.3.2. Sensitivity to noise

222 Although one of the advantages of downhole monitoring is the improvement in the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N),
 223 noise still needs to be considered especially during operations and especially since DAS recordings are generally
 224 noisier than standard geophone signals. Therefore, the influence of noise on the localisation accuracy is evalu-
 225 ated. Gaussian noise is added to the DAS signals using a normal distribution $\mathcal{N} = \mu + \sigma^2 \mathcal{Z}$, where \mathcal{Z} is the

Fig. 6: DAS signals for central source frequencies of (a) 50 Hz and (b) 100 Hz, and corresponding determined azimuth on channel 1 (top channel) to 44 (source-depth channel). Other source parameters are the same with the base example.

226 standard normal variable, $\mu = 0$ and σ is chosen from $1 \cdot 10^{-13}$, $4 \cdot 10^{-13}$ and $1 \cdot 10^{-12}$, leading to a S/N of 18.8
 227 dB, 7.7 dB and 2.5 dB, respectively.

228 Fig. 7 shows the signals with the different noise levels and the determined azimuth on each channel. Results
 229 suggest that when the noise level is at S/N = 18.8 dB, the accuracy of the determined average azimuth is
 230 acceptable, with an error of 2.9%. With an increasing noise level, the accuracy decreases significantly, with
 231 errors of 7.1% and 16.2% for the other two cases. The noise has a dramatic influence on the accuracy for
 232 channels close to the source depth (i.e. 500 m), the reason being that the strain at these channels becomes
 233 very small due to the wave motion being as-good-as perpendicular to the fibre, and then the noise dominates
 234 the localisation accuracy. One possible solution is to exclude these channels; however, as shown in Fig. 7f, the
 235 accuracy from the remaining channels also declines towards the source depth, albeit more gradually.

Fig. 7: DAS (strain) signals with noise levels of (a) S/N = 18.8 dB, (b) 7.7 dB and (c) S/N = 2.5 dB, and corresponding determined azimuth on channel 1 (top channel) to 44 (source-depth channel). Source parameters as in base example.

236 3.3.3. Sensitivity to azimuth

237 So far, the source to borehole azimuth was chosen as 45° . Since one of the main motivations to consider a
 238 single-well dual-cable DAS is to determine azimuth, it is necessary to examine the dependence of the localisation
 239 accuracy on this parameter. The source mechanism is assumed to be a vertical point force \mathbf{F}_z and therefore
 240 signals on the DAS cable will remain the same with changing azimuth. However, when the *difference* in the
 241 signals between DAS cable 1 and cable 2 is taken, it will vary with azimuth, as is illustrated in Figs. 8a - 8c.
 242 The results are consistent with the relation depicted in Fig. 3, showing that the largest difference corresponds
 243 to an azimuth of 0° while a zero difference corresponds to 90° . The accuracy of the localised azimuth increases
 244 with the azimuth approaching 90° , as is shown in Figs. 8d - 8f, with errors of 45%, 4%, 0.8% for azimuths of
 245 15° , 45° and 75° respectively. The reason is that, as shown in Fig. 3, the slope of the curve of the relation
 246 between ΔL and θ decreases when θ approaches 0° , leading to an insensitivity to the change in azimuth. In
 247 contrast, the slope reaches its maximum value when $\theta = 90^\circ$, therefore having the highest accuracy in the
 248 localisation. Additional constraints from surface receivers or a third DAS cable in the borehole can well resolve
 249 the low accuracy in locating the azimuth close to 0° .

Fig. 8: Difference in DAS signals between DAS cable 1 and cable 2 with a source-to-borehole azimuth of (a) 15°, (b) 45° and (c) 75°, and corresponding determined azimuth on channel 1 (top channel) to 44 (source-depth channel). Other source parameters are the same with the base example.

3.3.4. Sensitivity to force-source mechanism

In the above when the observed $\Delta NRMS^m$ is matched with the theoretical $\Delta NRMS$, the source mechanism was assumed to be $\mathbf{F} = F_0 \mathbf{e}_z$, consistent with the source mechanism of the observed $\Delta NRMS^m$. However, source mechanisms vary, and therefore it is necessary to evaluate how the localisation accuracy responds to different source mechanisms. Here we only consider other force-source mechanisms, and we exclude forces in the y -direction since source with force in the x direction shows the same nature.

Here, we let the source mechanisms vary from $\mathbf{F} = F_0 \mathbf{e}_z$ (Fig. 4a), $\mathbf{F} = F_0 \mathbf{e}_x$ (Fig. 9a) and $\mathbf{F} = F_0 (\mathbf{e}_x + \mathbf{e}_z)$ (Fig. 9b). The corresponding determined azimuths are shown in Fig. 5b, 9c and 9d respectively. The results indicate that the highest localization accuracy is achieved when the source mechanism of the observed $\Delta NRMS^m$ and the theoretical $\Delta NRMS$ match (both being $F_0 \mathbf{e}_z$, Fig. 5b). The worst match is when the source mechanism is $F_0 \mathbf{e}_x$ (Fig. 9c) with an error of 11.3%. Fig. 9d shows a better localization accuracy for the case of $\mathbf{F} = F_0 \mathbf{e}_x + F_0 \mathbf{e}_z$ than the case of $\mathbf{F} = F_0 \mathbf{e}_z$, because of the presence of the $F_0 \mathbf{e}_z$ component in the source, which helps to maintain accuracy.

Fig. 9: DAS (strain) signals with source mechanism of (a) $\mathbf{F} = F_0\mathbf{e}_x$ and (b) $\mathbf{F} = F_0\mathbf{e}_x + F_0\mathbf{e}_z$, and corresponding determined azimuth on channel 1 (top channel) to 44 (broadside channel). Other source parameters are the same with the base example.

263 4. Moment-tensor Resolvability

264 In a previous study by Vera Rodriguez and Wuestefeld (2020), the resolvability of the moment tensor was
 265 investigated with two well-separated boreholes. Here, we investigate what happens when the two DAS cables
 266 are within one borehole, with the results from Vera Rodriguez and Wuestefeld (2020) used as a reference case. In
 267 this section, we show how to construct the resolution matrix from semi-analytical solution (via the code CPS).
 268 Although the discussion in this feasibility study is limited to homogeneous and isotropic media for simplicity,
 269 the proposed method to construct the resolution matrix can be used to study inhomogeneous and anisotropic
 270 media.

271 4.1. Construction of the resolution matrix

272 Source mechanism inversion includes retrieving the source time function and moment tensor. Since the primary
 273 goal of this work is to evaluate the resolvability of the time-independent moment tensor only, the time dependence
 274 of the source process is not considered (Vavryčuk and Kühn, 2012; Chapman and Leaney, 2012), thus simplifying
 275 the problem to linear moment-tensor inversion. The moment-tensor components can be linearly related with
 276 the observed data by (Vavryčuk and Kühn, 2012; Vera Rodriguez and Wuestefeld, 2020):

$$\mathbf{G}\mathbf{m} = \mathbf{d} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{M} = [M_{xx}, M_{xy}, M_{xz}, M_{yy}, M_{yz}, M_{zz}]$ is the model vector composed of six unknown independent moment tensor components to be retrieved. $\mathbf{d} = [d_1, d_2, \dots, d_N]$ is the data vector consisting of the observed strain amplitude on DAS (in this work, z component of strain), and N is the number of channels. \mathbf{G} is the geometry matrix, and can be expanded as:

$$\mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} G_{11} & G_{12} & G_{13} & G_{14} & G_{15} & G_{16} \\ G_{21} & G_{22} & G_{23} & G_{24} & G_{25} & G_{26} \\ & & \dots & \dots & & \\ G_{N1} & G_{N2} & G_{N3} & G_{N4} & G_{N5} & G_{N6} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

In this work, \mathbf{G} is constructed from semi-analytical solution calculated from CPS (Herrmann, 2013) that gives the complete solution. Taking the i th channel as an example, the elements can be described as:

$$\begin{aligned} G_{i1} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[\frac{Z_{SS}}{2} \cos(2\phi) - \frac{Z_{DD}}{6} + \frac{Z_{EX}}{3} \right]_i \\ G_{i2} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial z} [Z_{SS} \sin(2\phi)]_i \\ G_{i3} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial z} [Z_{DS} \cos \phi]_i \\ G_{i4} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[-\frac{Z_{SS}}{2} \cos(2\phi) - \frac{Z_{DD}}{6} + \frac{Z_{EX}}{3} \right]_i \\ G_{i5} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial z} [Z_{DS} \sin \phi]_i \\ G_{i6} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[\frac{Z_{DD}}{3} + \frac{Z_{EX}}{3} \right]_i \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where ϕ is the azimuth angle. Z_{SS} is the function of the response to a strike-slip source, Z_{DS} represents the response to a vertical dip-slip source, Z_{DD} can be understood as part of a vertical or radial displacements for a 45° dip-slip source observed at an azimuth of 45° , and Z_{EX} represents the response to an explosive source (Jost and Herrmann, 1989; Herrmann, 2013).

When the data contain noise or other signal not covered by the modelling, then Eq. 4 can be solved by the least-squares solution, as was done in Vera Rodriguez and Wuestefeld (2020), so:

$$\mathbf{M} = [\mathbf{G}^T \mathbf{G}]^{-1} \mathbf{G}^T \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{G}^T \mathbf{d} \quad (7)$$

and the so-called resolution matrix is accordingly constructed as:

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{A}^\dagger \mathbf{A}, \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{A}^\dagger is the pseudoinverse of matrix \mathbf{A} , which is equal to \mathbf{A} when all the elements in the model vector \mathbf{m} are linearly independent and resolvable (Vera Rodriguez and Wuestefeld, 2020). Thus, the resolution matrix

292 \mathbf{R} indicates the resolvability of the moment tensor components. When \mathbf{R} is not the identity, its diagonal
 293 elements with value of 1 indicate that the corresponding moment tensor components are fully resolvable, while
 294 its diagonal elements with value of 0 indicate that the corresponding moment tensor components are completely
 295 not resolvable. In addition, non-zero off-diagonal values indicate linear dependence between two components.

296 Some of the diagonal elements with a value of 1 can correspond to extremely small values (due to noise or
 297 near-field terms when being in the far field), indicating that the related moment-tensor component cannot be
 298 resolved robustly. It is reported in [Nolen-Hoeksema and Ruff \(2001\)](#) that satisfactory inversion results can be
 299 obtained when the condition number (ratio of the largest singular value to the smallest, in our case of square
 300 symmetric matrices the largest eigenvalue to the smallest) of \mathbf{A}^\dagger is smaller than 500. Thus, each non-zero
 301 eigenvalue is evaluated by computing the ratio of the largest eigenvalue to it. If this ratio exceeds 500, the
 302 corresponding element of the resolution matrix is forced to be smaller than 1 so that all the elements of 1 in
 303 the resolution matrix indicate the corresponding moment tensor component can be reliably resolved.

304 4.2. Moment-tensor resolvability from a single DAS cable in a vertical borehole

305 In this section, the resolution matrix is constructed for the case of one DAS cable in a vertical borehole. This
 306 resolvability analysis is performed to be compared with the results from [Vera Rodriguez and Wuestefeld \(2020\)](#)
 307 to verify our method and demonstrate why some of the diagonal elements with a value 1 in the resolution matrix
 308 cannot be viewed as an indication of reliable resolvable moment tensor components. The source and the DAS
 309 cable are in the $x - z$ or North-Down plane with an azimuth of 0° (i.e. the fibre is to the North of the source)
 310 at epicentral distances ranging from 5 m to 100 m. The other aspects of the configuration including source
 311 parameters, DAS positions and gauge length are the same as in the base example.

312 The resolution matrix is obtained for both P and S wave separately, by evaluating the \mathbf{G} matrix at corresponding
 313 theoretical arrival time.

314 Fig. 10 demonstrates that four components (M_{xx} , M_{xz} , M_{yy} and M_{zz}) are resolvable from the P wave when
 315 the epicentral distance is 5 m or 10 m. In contrast, when the epicentral is 40 m, only three components (i.e.
 316 M_{xx} , M_{xz} and M_{zz}) are resolvable from the P-wave, showing consistent results with the analytical solution
 317 from [Vera Rodriguez and Wuestefeld \(2020\)](#), in which results show the component M_{yy} can only be retrieved
 318 when the intermediate-field term is included in the solution. In addition, the constraints provided by S wave is
 319 redundant, mostly useful only to improve the robustness of the solution ([Vera Rodriguez and Wuestefeld, 2020](#)).

320 Fig. 11 show the influence of increasing epicentral distance on the condition number, defined as the ratio of the
 321 largest to smallest non-zero eigenvalues. It shows that the condition number is smaller than 500 only when the
 322 epicentral distance is 5 or 10 m. This is because the near- and intermediate-field terms have minor contributions
 323 beyond the area of 10 m, while M_{yy} cannot be resolved robustly with only far-field terms ([Vera Rodriguez and](#)
 324 [Wuestefeld, 2020](#)). In addition, a smaller condition number for the P-wave signal compared to that for the S-wave
 325 signal can be observed because the P-wave signal gives more constraint, as is shown in Fig. 10. Interestingly,
 326 when the epicentral distance increases up to 40-100 m, the condition number shows an oscillatory pattern. The
 327 reason for this is that the numerical noise now plays a role as the signals weaken. This trend is also evident
 328 in Fig. 12, which depicts the DAS signals from an M_{yy} source gradually fading into the noise background as

329 the epicentral distance increases. The P-wave signal is much weaker and therefore shows more sensitivity to the
 330 noise than S-wave signal in this case.

Fig. 10: Resolution matrix of P-wave (top row) and S-wave (bottom row) signal for different epicentral distances for the case of one DAS cable in a vertical borehole. The configuration geometry is that the source and the DAS cable is in the $x - z$ plane, so that the source to DAS azimuth is 0° . The epicentral distance is 5 (left column), 10 (middle column), and 40 m (right column).

Fig. 11: Condition number of matrix \mathbf{A}^\dagger for different epicentral distances.

Fig. 12: Strain signals on one DAS cable in a vertical borehole due to a M_{yy} source for different epicentral distances. Source and DAS cable are in the $x - z$ plane. With increasing epicentral distance, signals weaken and become comparable to the numerical noise background. P-wave signal is much weaker and therefore shows more sensitivity to the noise than S-wave signal in this case.

331 Next, the influence of the source to DAS-cable azimuth angle on the resolvability is investigated, assuming
 332 an epicentral distance of 40 m. This is shown in Fig. 13. It shows reasonably well that when the azimuth
 333 is 0° , M_{xx} , M_{xz} and M_{zz} are resolvable, while at 90° , M_{yy} , M_{yz} and M_{zz} are resolvable. In addition, when
 334 the azimuth is 45° , neither M_{xx} nor M_{yy} is resolvable, since both produce identical DAS signals and are thus
 335 linearly dependent, as is indicated by the off-diagonal non-zero elements.

Fig. 13: Resolution matrix of P-wave (top row) and S-wave (bottom row) for different azimuths for the case of one DAS cable in a vertical borehole. The epicentral distance is fixed at 40 m, while the source to DAS azimuth is 0° (left column), 45° (middle column) and 90° (right column).

337 The above discussion demonstrated that the moment tensor cannot be fully resolved from a single vertical DAS
 338 cable, although at a smaller epicentral distance, near- and intermediate-field terms can improve the resolvability
 339 of some of the components, showing results consistent with previous studies (Vavryčuk, 2007; Vera Rodriguez
 340 et al., 2011; Vera Rodriguez and Wuestefeld, 2020). In this section, the resolvability from the dual cable in one
 341 single vertical well is examined. In the previous section, the DAS cable lay in the same plane as the source.
 342 In this configuration, an additional cable will not improve the focal coverage which refers to the capability of
 343 the network of seismic sensors to constrain source location and mechanism. Therefore, we assume that the
 344 configuration is as shown in Fig. 14. That is, the source-to-borehole azimuth is 90° , located West of the
 345 borehole, while the two DAS cables are placed at opposite sides of the borehole, i.e., in the North and South.

Fig. 14: Schematic diagrams of the horizontal cross-section of the dual-cable configuration in a vertical well. Source to borehole azimuth is 90° .

346 The borehole diameter (d) and the epicentral distance (D_0) together control the focal coverage, while a shorter
 347 epicentral distance will also lead to stronger near- and intermediate-field terms that can improve the moment-
 348 tensor resolvability. In this section, the epicentral distance is first assumed to be 40 m to limit the effects of
 349 near- and intermediate-field terms, and we examine the effects of the borehole diameter on the improvement of
 350 the moment-tensor resolvability from a dual cable, compared to one cable only. The effects of the epicentral
 351 distance with a fixed borehole diameter will be examined afterwards.

352 Fig. 15 compares the resolvability of moment-tensor components from one DAS cable to the one from two
 353 DAS cables in a single vertical well, with varying borehole diameter and a fixed epicentral distance of 40 m.
 354 These diameters are chosen since 0.5 m is a reasonable value for deep boreholes while 2.5 m is a value of an
 355 expanded borehole reported in Van der Schans et al. (2022). The results demonstrate that with increasing the
 356 borehole diameter, additional components can be resolved with dual DAS cable in a single vertical well. But
 357 only when the diameter reaches 2.5 m, the component M_{xy} can additionally be resolved with robust resolution.
 358 This indicates that only installation of a dual DAS cable in shallow and expanded boreholes can improve the
 359 moment-tensor resolvability of a source that is triggered tens of meters away from the borehole. Considering

360 that many geothermal doublets consist of two wells drilled at a close distance, it is also promising to install a
 361 DAS cable in each well to improve the moment-tensor resolvability. Since we are interested in the downhole
 362 micro-seismic monitoring in a vertical and deep well, the resolvability of near-borehole sources is next examined
 363 with a small borehole diameter ($d = 0.5$ m).

Fig. 15: Comparison of resolution matrix from one (left column) and dual (right column) DAS cables for different borehole diameters of 0.5 (top row), 1.5 (middle row) and 2.5 m (bottom row), assuming an epicentral distance of 40 m and source-borehole azimuth of 90° .

364 Fig. 16 compares the resolvability of near-borehole sources (with epicentral distance of 5 m, 10 m and 20 m)
 365 from one DAS cable and two DAS cables in a single vertical well, with a borehole diameter of 0.5 m. The results
 366 show that employing a dual-cable DAS configuration can resolve one additional component compared to the
 367 one-cable configuration for all the cases considered. In particular, if the source is 5 m away from the borehole,
 368 the moment tensor can be fully resolved from the dual-cable DAS configuration. With increasing epicentral
 369 distance, the number of resolvable components decreases. However, the dual-cable DAS configuration can

370 guarantee the resolvability of the non-Double-Couple (non-DC) components (i.e. M_{xx} , M_{yy} , M_{zz}) even with an
 371 epicentral distance up to 20 m. The non-DC components determine the tensile failure of the events, therefore
 372 crucial for the application of monitoring micro-seismic events induced by reinjection/stimulation operations,
 373 during which tensile cracking events are most likely to happen in the near-borehole area. Therefore, installing
 374 a dual-cable DAS configuration can be concluded to provide valuable information.

Fig. 16: Comparison of resolution matrix from one and two DAS cables with different epicentral distances, assuming a borehole diameter of 0.5 m.

375 5. Discussion

376 The dual-cable DAS configuration proposed in this work has the potential to fully locate near-borehole rock
 377 failures, although at certain conditions (e.g. low S/N or azimuth close to 0° , i.e. aligned to the two cables) the
 378 accuracy decreases. Yet, the accuracy under these conditions can be improved by an additional constraints from

379 either surface receivers or a third DAS cable in the well. In addition, advanced arrival-picking techniques (for
380 determining depth and epicentral distance, see section 3.2) and noise suppressing techniques can improve the
381 localisation accuracy. The localisation method with the dual-cable DAS configuration is shown to be valid for
382 a source with centre frequency from 50 Hz to 200 Hz, which, from literature, is commonly the dominant range
383 of micro-seismic events induced during reinjection or small-scale stimulation operations. Compared to the case
384 of only a single DAS cable, the additional constraint of the azimuth, due to the installation of the dual-cable
385 DAS, can therefore provide valuable information on the in-situ stress state, the stress rotation and fracture
386 propagation during operations. The full constraint on the location is also necessary to invert for the moment
387 tensor to better understand the source mechanisms.

388 To construct the resolution matrix, the semi-analytical semi-numerical solution from CPS was used. This
389 allows us to study inhomogeneous and anisotropic horizontally layered media, although our study is limited to
390 homogenous and isotropic media in this paper for simplicity. The analysis of the moment-tensor resolvability
391 shows that the installation of a dual-cable can help us to constrain the non-DC moment tensor components M_{xx} ,
392 M_{yy} and M_{zz} with an epicentral distance of, in this study, up to 20 m from the borehole. In contrast, for the DC
393 components, M_{xy} and M_{xz} cannot be resolved with robust resolution with increasing epicentral distance while
394 M_{yz} can be constrained even with an epicentral distance of 40 m. As mentioned early, the non-DC components
395 indicate tensile failures while DC components indicate pure shear failures. Previous studies have shown non-DC
396 components are related to the formation of hydraulic fractures (Šílený et al., 2009), while DC components are
397 linked to re-activation and development of natural fractures in shear mode (Sasaki, 1998). During hydraulic
398 stimulation of homogeneous and non-fractured reservoirs, tensile failures dominate the micro-seismic response
399 (Hampton et al., 2018; Baird et al., 2020; Tanaka et al., 2021; Butt et al., 2024).

400 To demonstrate the ability to monitor a stimulation campaign, a 2-D geo-mechanical simulation (assuming
401 vertical fracture under normal-faulting environment) of thermal stimulation is performed to predict the tensile
402 fractures in the near-borehole region. These fractures are then described by a moment tensor, which, based on
403 the resolvability analysis, gives information about its resolvability via the dual-cable DAS. The moment tensors
404 are then decomposed into elementary tensors to facilitate the interpretation. The following discussion focuses
405 on tensile fractures, while the same procedure works also for shear fracture, which is not discussed here.

406 The problem of the thermal stimulation, together with the numerical model and input data, is presented in
407 Appendix B. An example simulation result is presented in Fig. 17a, showing three main fractures induced
408 around the borehole at the end of the simulation ($t = 120$ h). Fracture B propagates in the direction of the
409 maximum initial stress σ_H and is the longest of the fractures, while fractures A and C propagate in the directions
410 of 135° and 45° , respectively. With the fracture propagation, micro-seismicity will be continuously generated
411 (Butt et al., 2024). The micro-seismicity generated by the propagation of the induced main fractures A , B and
412 C in Fig. 17a can therefore be described by the following moment tensor:

$$\mathbf{M}_A = \frac{1}{2}M_0 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{M}_B = M_0 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{M}_C = \frac{1}{2}M_0 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

413 where M_0 [N·m] is the seismic moment, which is a quantitative measure of the amount of energy released in an
 414 seismic event, i.e., of the micro-seismicity resulted from the fracture opening. It is assumed that all the energy
 415 released due to the tensile fracture is transferred to seismic energy. Therefore, the seismic moment M_0 can be
 416 calculated from the specific fracture energy.

417 As is discussed earlier in relation to Fig. 16, the non-DC components M_{xx} and M_{yy} can be resolved at 20 m
 418 away from the borehole using the dual-cable DAS in a single vertical well, while M_{xy} can only be resolved at
 419 distances of 10 m or less. Therefore, only the initiation and propagation of fracture B can be well monitored
 420 and understood at a distance further than 20 m. The initiation and source mechanisms of fractures A and C
 421 can only be understood if they happen within 10 m, i.e. indicating a process of multiple fractures. The moment
 422 tensor can be decomposed into three elementary tensors, i.e. ISO, DC, and CLVD (Vavryčuk, 2015), and be
 423 represented in Hudson's source-type plot. The details of the decomposition is presented in Appendix C. The
 424 decomposition of the moment tensors of three micro-seismic events resulted from the propagation of the three
 425 tensile fractures during the thermal stimulation is depicted in Hudson's source-type plot as is shown in Fig.
 426 17b. The three tensile fractures contain the same portion of CLVD + and Explosion components, regardless
 427 of their different fracture directions. The results imply that the near-borehole tensile fractures induced during
 428 either geothermal operations or thermal stimulation can be characterised using the dual-cable DAS in a single
 429 vertical well, with the direction of fracture well resolved. However, the identification of the full moment tensor,
 430 which identifies the type of fracture (and therefore connecting to the changes in permeability) depends on the
 431 epicentral distance orientation of the two DAS cables. Several components of the moment can however be
 432 identified, and knowledge of the initial in-situ stresses and stress path imposed could be sufficient to estimate
 433 the moment tensor. Placing the two DAS cables aligned with the the direction of the maximum in-situ stress is
 434 the most advantageous choice, since it improves the focal coverage, and is shown to be able to identify tensile
 435 fractures.

Fig. 17: (a) Tensile fractures are induced in the near-borehole region to connect the borehole to the un-damaged zone, and (b) the positions of the corresponding generated micro-seismic events on the Hudson's source-type plot.

436 6. Conclusions

437 In this work, the configuration of a dual DAS cable in a single vertical well is proposed to provide constraints
438 on source location and moment tensor that are additional to the case of a single DAS cable. The configuration
439 consists of two DAS cables at opposite sides in one single vertical well. Synthetic signals are generated using
440 an open-source code that assumes plane-layered media. A localisation method is introduced and demonstrated
441 with a reference case to show the feasibility of using the difference in the signals of two DAS cables to determine
442 source depth, epicentral distance and azimuth. Sensitivity analysis shows that a low S/N and azimuth close to
443 0° can lead to decreasing localisation accuracy, while the accuracy of the method is not sensitive to frequencies
444 varying from 50 Hz to 200 Hz. In addition, the resolvability of the moment tensor is analysed, and results
445 suggest non-DC components M_{xx} , M_{yy} and M_{zz} can be reliably resolved if the source epicentral distance is
446 within 20 meters, showing improvement on the case of only one DAS cable in a well. Resolvability of the DC
447 components M_{xy} and M_{xz} are more sensitive to large distances, since near- and intermediate-terms play an
448 essential role to constrain additional components.

449 The two DAS cables within one well are optimally positioned in the direction of minimal horizontal stresses
450 in normal-faulting geological condition. Geo-mechanical simulation shows tensile fractures can be induced in
451 a homogeneous and non-fractured reservoir during thermal stimulation. The propagation of the main tensile
452 fracture in the direction of maximum initial stress σ_H that happens within 20 m can be well monitored and un-
453 derstood, while the understanding of the tensile fracture branching in other directions relies on the resolvability
454 of the moment tensor component M_{xy} . The results demonstrate that a single-well dual-cable configuration has
455 the potential for monitoring and understanding near-borehole micro-seismic events induced during geothermal
456 reinjection and stimulation operations.

457 Author Contributions

458 **Wen Luo:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal Analysis, Data Curation, Writing -
459 Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization.

460 **Guy Drijkoningen:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Software, Formal Analysis, Writing - Review & Editing,
461 Supervision, Funding Acquisition.

462 **Mahmoud Eltayieb:** Software, Formal Analysis, Writing - Review & Editing.

463 **Florian Amann:** Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding Acquisition.

464 **Philip J. Vardon:** Conceptualisation, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Project Administration,
465 Funding Acquisition.

466 Declaration of competing interest

467 Wen Luo reports financial support was provided by European Commission. Mahmoud Eltayieb reports financial
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475 Appendix A. Details of the pre-computed Δ_{NRMS}

476 Here we describe the details of the determination of the pre-computed Δ_{NRMS} , based on the specific case in
477 Section 3.2. Forward modellings are run to get a series of Δ_{NRMS} , consisting of Δ_{NRMS} between the signals of
478 the m th channel on cable 1 and the signals of the m th channel on a cable whose m th channel is at a distance of
479 ($D_1^m + V_s \cdot i \cdot dt$) to the source. D_1^m is the distance from the source to the m th channel on DAS cable 1 (D_2^m can
480 also be used). V_s is the S-wave velocity (P-wave velocity can also be used) assumed to be known a priori, dt
481 is the time increment between the two adjacent pre-computed Δ_{NRMS} , and determines the resolution. i is the
482 number of the time steps. The value of dt depends on the desired determination resolution and the capability
483 of the pre-computing code (here CPS) to capture the difference. The maximum number of time steps, i , is
484 determined by the borehole diameter d and the selected time increment dt so that ($i * dt = < d$) is satisfied.
485 Since the borehole diameter is 0.5 m and dt is 0.01 ms in our case, $i = 30$ can ensure the largest ΔL^m included.
486 When pre-computing the Δ_{NRMS} , source depth, epicentral distance and frequency can be determined from
487 previous steps, while the source mechanism is assumed to be $\mathbf{F} = F_0 \mathbf{e}_z$, consistent with the source mechanism
488 of the synthetic signals on DAS cable 1 and cable 2.

489 Appendix B. Details of the geo-mechanical modelling

490 A highly permeable reservoir is modelled, inspired by Delft Sandstone Formation (Vardon et al., 2024). The
491 properties of the reservoir are shown in Tab. B.2 and the model parameters are shown in Tab. B.3. A
492 clogged zone with radius of 5 m is assumed considering regional experience of injectivity decline due to, for
493 example, chemical scaling. Thermal stimulation is simulated to stimulate the clogged zone and induce fractures
494 to connect the borehole to the un-clogged zone. The synthetic thermal stimulation scenario is: $Q_{inj} = 360 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$
495 with injection temperature $T_{inj} = 308 \text{ K}$ over a period of 5 days.

496 The domain of the geo-mechanical model is a half circle (due to symmetry) with a radius of 500 m, representing
497 the sedimentary geothermal reservoir, and to impose reasonable far-field boundary conditions. A half borehole

498 with a diameter of 0.5 m is placed at the centre of the domain. Boundary and initial conditions are presented
499 in Fig. 18a. The initial stresses are $\sigma_h = 38$ MPa in x direction (North) while $\sigma_H = 42$ MPa in y direction
500 (East). The displacement at the bottom boundaries is fixed in y direction due to symmetry, while at the far-
501 field boundaries the displacement is fixed in both x and y directions. A uniform normal load, which is equal
502 to the steady-state injection pressure, is distributed along the borehole throughout the simulation time. In
503 addition to the mechanical boundary conditions, temperature and pressure are fixed at initial values at far-field
504 boundaries. The domain is meshed with continuum finite elements, with interface elements inserted in between
505 all the continuum elements in the inner region with a radius of 10 m to allow arbitrary fracture initiation and
506 propagation in the near-borehole area while to avoid inserting interface elements in all over the domain which
507 will result in heavy computational burden. The mathematical formulations of the discontinuous problem under
508 coupled thermo-hydro-mechanical processes and their finite element procedure can be found in our previous
509 publication (Luo et al., 2025), and will not be repeated here.

Fig. 18: (a) Geo-mechanical model with initial and boundary conditions. Interface elements are inserted in between all the continuum elements only within the inner region with a radius of 10 meters. Outside this region, only continuum elements exist. (b) the tensile branch of the elasto-damage constitutive law which governs the mechanical response of the interface element. The shadowed area under the solid line is the specific fracture energy, which can be used to calculate the seismic moment, assuming all fracture energy is transferred to radiated seismic energy.

Table B.2: Data of the targeted Delft Sandstone Formation and reservoir rock (Aramburo Velez, 2017; Soustelle et al., 2022; Voskov et al., 2024; Vardon et al., 2024). Some from internal reports.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit	Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Vertical stress	σ_v	48	MPa	Rock Young's modulus	E	11.5	GPa
Max. horizontal stress	σ_H	42	MPa	Rock Poisson's ratio	ν	0.15	-
Min. horizontal stress	σ_h	38	MPa	Rock compressive strength	σ_c	48	MPa
Pore water pressure	p_{ini}	21	MPa	Rock tensile strength*	σ_t	4.8	MPa
Reservoir temperature	T_{ini}	353	K	Rock thermal expansion coeff.	β	6.5E-5	K ⁻¹
Reservoir permeability	k	1.6	D	Rock heat conductivity	λ	3	W/(m·K)
Reservoir porosity	ϕ	0.17	-	Rock heat capacity	c_{ps}	2450	KJ/(m ³ ·K)
Reservoir thickness	H	100	m	Rock density	ρ_s	2650	kg/m ³

*: σ_t is assumed to be 1/10 of σ_c , which is derived from logging data.

Table B.3: Input parameters for the interface elements used in the model

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Tensile strength	σ_{n0}	4.8	MPa
Cracking separation	r_{n0}	1E-7	m
Debonding separation	r_{nc}	1E-6	m
Mechanical viscosity	ζ	1E14	Pa·s/m
Parameter a	a	-	-
Parameter b	b	-	-
Initial aperture	w_0	1E-5	m
Initial longitudinal transmissivity	t_0^l	1.6E-17	m ³
Initial transversal transmissivity	$t_0^{b/t}$	1E-10	m ²

510 Appendix C. Details of the moment tensor decomposition

511 The moment tensor can be decomposed into three elementary tensors, i.e. ISO, DC, and CLVD as follows
 512 (Vavryčuk, 2015):

$$\mathbf{M}' = M_{\text{ISO}}\mathbf{E}_{\text{ISO}} + M_{\text{DC}}\mathbf{E}_{\text{DC}} + M_{\text{CLVD}}\mathbf{E}_{\text{CLVD}} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

513 where \mathbf{M}' is the principal moment tensor in the principal coordinate system, and \mathbf{E}_{ISO} , \mathbf{E}_{DC} and \mathbf{E}_{CLVD} are
 514 the ISO, DC and CLVD elementary tensors, and read:

$$\mathbf{E}_{\text{ISO}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{E}_{\text{DC}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{E}_{\text{CLVD}}^+ = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{or} \quad \mathbf{E}_{\text{CLVD}}^- = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{C.2})$$

515 where $\mathbf{E}_{\text{CLVD}}^+$ or $\mathbf{E}_{\text{CLVD}}^-$ is used if $M_1 + M_3 - 2M_2 \geq 0$ or $M_1 + M_3 - 2M_2 < 0$ (M_1 , M_2 and M_3 are the
 516 eigenvalues of the principal moment tensor \mathbf{M}' and $M_1 \geq M_2 \geq M_3$). The corresponding elementary scalar
 517 moments read:

$$M_{\text{ISO}} = \frac{1}{3}(M_1 + M_2 + M_3), \quad M_{\text{DC}} = \frac{1}{2}(M_1 - M_3 - |M_1 + M_3 - 2M_2|), \quad M_{\text{CLVD}} = \frac{2}{3}(M_1 + M_3 - 2M_2) \quad (\text{C.3})$$

518 The values of M_{ISO} , M_{DC} and M_{ISO} are generally normalised to obtain the contribution of each elementary
 519 source mechanism:

$$\begin{bmatrix} C_{\text{ISO}} \\ C_{\text{DC}} \\ C_{\text{CLVD}} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{M} \begin{bmatrix} M_{\text{ISO}} \\ M_{\text{DC}} \\ M_{\text{CLVD}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{C.4})$$

520 where $M = |M_{\text{ISO}}| + |M_{\text{CLVD}}| + M_{\text{DC}}$, so that $|C_{\text{ISO}}| + |C_{\text{CLVD}}| + C_{\text{DC}} = 1$ is always satisfied. Physically,
521 $C_{\text{ISO}} = \pm 1$ indicates pure explosion/implosion. $C_{\text{DC}} = 1$ indicates pure shear failures while $C_{\text{DC}} = 0$ indicates
522 tensile failures that contain both ISO and CLVD components (Vavryčuk, 2015).

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